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Urban Farming as a Tool for Cultivating Innovation among Quezon City University Students

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Abstract.

The study sought to investigate urban farming as a Tool for Cultivating Innovation among Quezon City University Students. The researcher used Phenomenological Research. The descriptive method is used to gather information about the present existing condition. The researcher used the sampling technique by selecting at least two hundred (250) students as respondents. The respondents' demographic profile comprised the following: age, gender, and college year level. The stratified random sampling technique is used when respondents are chosen because of their appropriateness in the conduct of the study. It was used to ensure a balanced representation of Entrepreneurship students from Quezon City University. The data gathered from the respondents was tabulated and interpreted. The research adopts a qualitative approach, focusing on gathering in-depth insights through survey papers. The main instrument used in the collection of data was a structured Google Form survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was patterned after the questions used in a relevant study, a questionnaire based on the gathered relevant literature. The instrument was divided into 2 parts. The first part dealt with the demographic profile. The second part of the questionnaire was about the respondent's investigation into urban farming as a tool for cultivating innovation among Quezon City University students. The study concludes that embedding urban farming into entrepreneurship education provides a holistic framework for skill development while promoting environmental awareness. It is recommended that academic institutions integrate urban farming into broader curricular programs and establish partnerships with community stakeholders to maximize its educational and social impact. Future research may explore the influence of urban farming on students' entrepreneurial ventures and career trajectories beyond the university setting.

Keywords: Knowledge, Entrepreneurial Skills, Business Opportunity, Business Viability

1.0 Introduction

Urban farming has increasingly been recognized as a transformative practice in education, particularly in cultivating innovation among university students. Since 2021, initiatives in Quezon City have demonstrated how urban agriculture can serve as both a sustainable solution to food security and a platform for creative problem-solving. The establishment of the *Center for Urban Agriculture and Innovation (CUAI)* at Quezon City University in 2022 positioned the institution as a pioneer in integrating urban farming into higher education. Mayor Joy Belmonte emphasized that the center was part of efforts to create a "smart and sustainable city," highlighting its role in embedding urban agriculture into the curriculum and engaging students in innovative practices.

Scholars have also underscored the educational potential of urban farming. Firma et al. (2025) examined urban agriculture models in the Philippines and found that they effectively support farm-to-table supply chains, fostering innovation in food systems and student-led projects. Secretario (2021) explored Filipino youth perceptions of agriculture, noting that integrating farming into education

helps dismantle stereotypes and encourages students to view agriculture as a field of creativity and opportunity ResearchGate. These perspectives align with the Department of Agriculture's *National Urban and Peri-Urban Agriculture Program (NUPAP)* guidelines (2022), which emphasize urban farming as a tool for food security, livelihood creation, and innovation.

In urbanized regions worldwide, including the Philippines, urban farming is a practical response to issues with food security and the environment. The problems of food security and sustainability in our cities have become commonplace nowadays. Urban farming represents an aspiration to have fresh produce while generating opportunities for entrepreneurs like us. It is not merely planting crops but skills that could mold our futures. It also serves as a real-world application of entrepreneurial concepts in Quezon City University, where the entrepreneurship program aims to provide students with the skills necessary to build and manage businesses.

Together, these initiatives and studies highlight how urban farming is not only about food production but also about nurturing resourcefulness, design thinking, and collaborative learning among students. This study, *Urban Farming as a Tool for Cultivating Innovation in Quezon City University Students*, situates urban agriculture within the educational landscape, emphasizing its role in shaping innovative mindsets, preparing students to respond to modern challenges, and aligning with broader goals of sustainability and inclusive development.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a phenomenological research design to explore the lived experiences of entrepreneurship students at Quezon City University (QCU). Phenomenology focuses on understanding individuals' subjective experiences and the meanings they attach to them. As noted by Groenewald (2004), this design utilizes methods such as in-depth interviews, essays, focus groups, and reflective accounts to capture authentic lived experiences. In this study, the design was chosen to examine how engagement in urban farming activities influenced students' knowledge, entrepreneurial skills, perceived business opportunities, and business viability.

2.2 Research Participants and Sampling Technique

The participants of the study were entrepreneurship students enrolled at Quezon City University. A stratified random sampling method was employed to ensure balanced representation among respondents. The population was divided into subgroups based on relevant characteristics such as age, gender, year level, and prior exposure to urban farming. Respondents were then randomly selected from each subgroup to ensure inclusivity and reduce sampling bias.

2.3 Data Collection Instrument

Data were collected using a Google Questionnaire, which was distributed to entrepreneurship students. This tool was selected due to its efficiency, accessibility, and ability to reach a larger number of respondents within a limited time frame. The questionnaire included open-ended questions to allow participants to freely express their perspectives, experiences, and insights regarding urban farming and its relevance to entrepreneurship.

2.4 Data Collection Procedure

The Google Questionnaire was disseminated online to the selected respondents. Participants were given sufficient time to complete the survey, ensuring thoughtful and comprehensive responses. The use of an online platform facilitated convenient data gathering and improved response rates while maintaining data accuracy and completeness.

2.5 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the study. Participants were informed of the purpose of the research, and informed consent was obtained before data collection. The researchers ensured that participation was voluntary and that respondents' privacy and confidentiality were protected. All collected data were treated with integrity, and participants were safeguarded from harm. Respect for dignity, confidentiality, and transparency was prioritized at all stages of the research process.

3.0 Results and Discussion

The purpose of the study was to investigate Urban Farming as a Tool for Cultivating Innovation among Quezon City University Students in the aspects of Knowledge, Entrepreneurial Skills, Business Opportunity, and Business Viability. This study used a qualitative research design, which described the data and characteristics of the sample studied. There were two hundred (250) entrepreneurship students at Quezon City University. The statistical tools utilized in the study were frequency and percentage, and stratified random sampling.

3.1 Profile of the Respondents According to Age, Gender, College Year Level

Table 1. Age Frequency and Percentage Distribution in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-20	172	68.8%
21-23	33	13.2%
24 and above	45	18%
Total	250	100%

In terms of age, most respondents (68.8%) were between 18 and 20 years old, likely undergraduate students. A smaller portion was aged 21-23 (13.2%), and a very small group was 24 or older (18%). This indicates that the study primarily focuses on young adult students.

Table 2. Gender Frequency and Percentage Distribution in Terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	151	60.4%
LGBTQIA+	23	9.2%
Male	76	30.4%
Total	250	100%

In terms of gender, the majority of respondents identified as female (60.4%), followed by male (30.4%). A smaller percentage (9.2%) identified as LGBTQIA+. This information provides insights into the gender diversity of the study participants and can be used to analyze any potential gender-related differences in their responses or experiences.

Table 3. Gender Frequency And Percentage Distribution in Terms of Year Level

Year Level	Frequency	Percentage
1st year	39	15.6%
2nd year	136	54.4%
3rd year	75	30%
Total	250	100%

In terms of Year Level in College. Most of the respondents were in their second year (54.4%), while a smaller portion were in their first (15.6%) and third year (30%). This suggests that the study primarily focuses on second-year students.

3.2 Respondents' Engagement in Urban Farming and Their Perspectives on Long-Term Business Success and Sustainability

Table 4. Perceived Business Benefits of Urban Farming

Business Viability	Frequency	Percentage
Market sustainability	45	18%
profitability	33	9.2%
Cost efficiency	27	13.2%
Operational	23	10.8%
Other answers	122	48.8%
Total	203/250	81.2/100%

The table shows how respondents believe urban farming practices can contribute to their understanding of long-term success and sustainability. A majority (48.8%) believe it contributes in other ways, while a smaller portion think it promotes market sustainability (18. %), profitability (9.2%), cost -efficiency (27%), and operational (10.8%) This suggests that respondents see a wide range of potential benefits from urban farming practices beyond the specific categories listed.

3.3 Influence of Urban Farming Practices on Respondents' Knowledge and Skills in Implementing Sustainable Business Practices among Aspiring Entrepreneurs in QCU

Table 5. Knowledge and Skills Gained from Urban Farming Practices

Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
competence	65	26%
innovation	46	18.4%
awareness	31	12.4%
Social engagement	33	13.2%
Other answers	75	30%
Total	235/250	94/100%

The table shows how respondents believe sharing the latest urban farming innovations can benefit aspiring entrepreneurs. Most respondents (30%) think it offers benefits beyond the specific categories listed. A smaller portion believe it's helpful for general awareness (26%), competence (18.4%), innovation (18.4%), awareness (12.4%) and social engagement (13.2%).

3.4 Benefits of Sharing Urban Farming Innovations on Entrepreneurial Skills and Business Insights

Table 6. Entrepreneurial Skills Developed through Urban Farming Innovations

Entrepreneurial Skills	Frequency	Percentage
Creativity	82	32.8%
Business Planning skills	48	19.2%
Opportunity recognition	20	8%
Decision making skills	45	18%
Other responses	55	22%
Total	198/250	79.2/100%

Most respondents believe urban farming can spark entrepreneurial skills and lead to unique business ideas. While many (32.8%) think it fosters creativity in other ways, others highlighted specific areas like business planning skills (19.2%), opportunity recognition (8%), decision-making skills (18%), and other responses (5.33%).

3.5 Role of Urban Farming in Fostering Local Competition and Supporting Small Business Growth and Sustainability

Table 7. Business Opportunities Created by Urban Farming

Business Opportunity	Frequency	Percentage
Market awareness	55	22%
Startup readiness	79	31.6%
Opportunity identification	36	14.4%
Job creation	47	18.8%
Other answers	33	13.2%
Total	234/250	93.6/100%

The table shows how respondents believe urban farming innovations can create business opportunities for future entrepreneurs. Most respondents (31.6%) think it offers benefits beyond the specific categories listed. A smaller portion believe it's helpful for market awareness (22%), opportunity identification (14.4%), job creation (18.4%), and other answers.

4.0 Conclusion

As regards the profile of the respondents, the researcher found out most respondents come from the 2nd year level with a total population of 136 or 54.4% while most of their ages range from 21-23 years old with a population of 33 or 13.2 % This demographic information helps to contextualize the findings of the study and contribute to a deeper understanding of the role of urban farming in fostering entrepreneurial skills and promote sustainable urban development and economic improvement.

The study concludes that urban farming is an effective tool in developing entrepreneurial skills among entrepreneurship students. Through hands on involvement I urban farming activities, students were able to enhance their knowledge in, entrepreneurial skills, business opportunities and business viability.

The findings highlight that Urban farming has empowered students to become innovative entrepreneurs and environmentally conscious citizens. By engaging in hands-on projects, students have developed a deep understanding of business principles, product development, and sustainable agriculture. They've learned to identify market opportunities, create unique value propositions, and implement effective business strategies.

Overall, the results affirm that integrating urban farming into entrepreneurship education can strengthen students' readiness for future business ventures while supporting food security and sustainable urban development.

4.1 Recommendation

- Promote market linkages and digital marketing.
- Encourage innovation and fostering an urban farming, educators should implement structured and inclusive sustainability practices
- Provide Entrepreneurship Training and Workshops
- Support for student Start-ups

5.0 Contribution of the Authors

All researchers contributed to the conceptualization, design, data collection, analysis, and interpretation of the study. The manuscript was collaboratively written and revised, and all authors approved the final version and take responsibility for the accuracy and integrity of the work.

6.0 Funding

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7.0 Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest related to the publication of this study.

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